

Arctic Research Consortium of the U.S. (ARCUS)

Cooperative Agreement ARC-0618885

Annual Report

1 March 2012 - 28 February 2013

This document is the progress report for ARCUS' Cooperative Agreement, ARC-0618885, to provide organizational support to the NSF Arctic Sciences Section, Division of Polar Programs to develop, promote, and implement arctic research and education activities.

The narrative summarizes accomplishments for Year 5 of the Cooperative Agreement, 1 March 2012 - 28 February 2013; a budget report is included at the end of this document (note that the budget report is for the period 1 January 2012–31 December 2012).

The narrative organizes activities into five main task categories:

1. **Arctic Community Science Planning** – coordinating science planning for the arctic research community across disciplinary and organizational boundaries; includes Study of Environmental Arctic Change (SEARCH) Coordination and the Interagency Arctic Research Policy Committee (IARPC) tasks.
2. **Coordination Support for NSF Division of Arctic Sciences Programs** – coordination and support for the Division of Arctic Sciences programs; includes Arctic System Science (ARCSS) Program Coordination, Arctic Natural Science Program Coordination, Arctic Social Sciences Program Coordination, Arctic Section Science Materials, NSF's Forum of Arctic Research Operators (FARO) dues, and Research Support and Logistics workshop planning.
3. **Arctic Science Education** – development and coordination of arctic-focused educational activities; includes various Arctic Science Education Activities and the Arctic Visiting Speakers' Series.
4. **Information and Outreach** – information and outreach activities; includes *Witness the Arctic* newsletter, Website and Internet Resources, ArcticInfo mailing list, Directory of Arctic Researchers, Internet Media Archive, and Arctic Community Outreach.
5. **Core** – includes dedicated funding of the costs incurred by program activities that simultaneously support multiple cooperative agreement projects as well as Arctic Forum speaker support.

1. ARCTIC COMMUNITY SCIENCE PLANNING

1.1.a. SEARCH COORDINATION

The Study of Environmental Arctic Change (SEARCH) is an interagency effort to understand the nature, extent, and future development of the system-scale change presently seen in the Arctic. Major activities in this period included the Sea Ice Outlook, Sea Ice for Walrus Outlook, Arctic Observing Network tasks, strategic planning activities, and Science Steering Committee (SSC) management.

Sea Ice Outlook

The Sea Ice Outlook provides community-wide syntheses and projections of the arctic sea ice minimum throughout the summer.

- Planned and launched the 2012 Sea Ice Outlook with announcements via ArcticInfo and the SIO email list.
- Worked with H. Eicken, J. Overland, and contributing groups to develop, edit, organize, and publish the monthly reports, including full pan-arctic and regional reports and executive summaries.
- Announced reports via ArcticInfo, the SIO website, the SIO email list, and other relevant lists. Responded to queries from press; facilitated discussion amongst contributors and modeling groups.
- Developed a post-season report analyzing the season's events and Outlook accuracy.
- Maintained the Sea Ice Outlook electronic mailing list to provide a direct means for information dissemination and communication about the SIO and related news.
- Presented a Sea Ice Outlook/Sea Ice for Walrus Outlook poster at the American Geophysical Union 2012 Fall Meeting.

All 2012 Outlook reports are available at: <http://www.arcus.org/search/seaiceoutlook>

Sea Ice for Walrus Outlook

The Sea Ice for Walrus Outlook (SIWO) provides weekly ice forecasts for the Northern Bering Sea and southern Chukchi Sea regions of Alaska during walrus hunting season. The SIWO is a collaboration between SEARCH and the University of Alaska Fairbanks, the Eskimo Walrus Commission, the National Weather Service, and the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration.

- Worked with G. Hufford (NWS), N. Soreide (NOAA), T. Nakamura (NOAA), and H. Eicken (UAF) to compile, edit, and publish reports each Friday from 6 April–22 June 2012.

- Communicated with local community members to incorporate local observations in each weekly report.
- Announced the first report via ArcticInfo and the SIO mailing list. Each weekly report thereafter was announced via the SIO mailing list.
- Sent copies of the weekly reports via email to individuals in rural communities without high-speed Internet access.
- Worked with V. Metcalf at the Eskimo Walrus Commission to expand the list of contacts in rural communities.
- Provided weekly updates to the SIWO Facebook page:
<http://www.facebook.com/seaiceforwalrus>.

All of the 2012 reports can be found on the SIWO website at: <http://www.arcus.org/search/siwo>.

Strategic Planning Activities

In 2010, with several years experience as the SEARCH project office, ARCUS staff held the opinion that SEARCH efforts were suffering from a lack of focus in the program—rather than trying to implement a program that tackles all the issues under “arctic environmental change,” a more focused set of topics were required around which activities could be organized. Therefore, ARCUS authored a memo to NSF and the SEARCH SSC recommending a SEARCH Strategic Planning process. NSF and SEARCH leadership acted on this recommendation to define a tractable, well-defined set of goals and activities. As a result, the SEARCH SSC, with input from the broader community and agencies and facilitation from ARCUS, has developed a new vision and mission and a set of well-defined 5-year science goals and objectives. Specific activities over the reporting period include:

- Worked with SSC members and others to edit and finalize the goals and objectives based on input from the broader research community and agency representatives; the current goals and objectives can be found at: <http://www.arcus.org/search/goals>.
- Organized and led a small SSC meeting in October 2012 in Fairbanks, Alaska, to develop a conceptual framework and a plan for activities to implement the new SEARCH vision and mission. The outcomes of the meeting were:
 - Agreement on future SEARCH activities and products.
 - Agreement on a new organizational structure and process.
 - Development of the components for a draft implementation plan.
- Worked with the SSC members to develop a white paper summarizing ideas for future SEARCH activities and focus.
- Communicated with members of the broader arctic research community on the components of the white paper.

- Developed a four-page summary of SEARCH plans for agency representatives (H. Eicken used this summary to discuss SEARCH planning with agencies).
- Organized a Town Hall at the AGU Fall 2012 meeting to discuss SEARCH goals, objectives, and activities; over 80 participants attended. Presented a SEARCH poster and organized and convened an SSC side meeting to discuss and respond to feedback received at the Town Hall.

Arctic Observing Network (AON) Activities

The Arctic Observing Network (AON) is a critical part of the SEARCH portfolio. ARCUS, as the SEARCH project office, completed tasks to further advance AON to a science-driven, coordinated activity.

- **AON Design and Implementation** – ARCUS provided organizational and logistics support for an AON Design and Implementation Task Force, which was convened by NSF to provide guidance on how to achieve a well-designed and effective Arctic Observing System.
 - Worked with the ADI Task Force to plan, organize, and implement a small ADI workshop in June 2012 to discuss the final report. ARCUS staff did not attend the meeting, but participated in key sessions via phone.
 - Worked with the ADI Task Force to develop the ADI final report, "Designing, Optimizing, and Implementing an Arctic Observing Network." The report can be viewed or downloaded online, at: <http://www.arcus.org/search/aon/adi>. Distributed and announced the report.
- **U.S. Arctic Observing Coordination Workshop** - ARCUS organized a U.S. Arctic Observing Coordination Workshop March 2012 in Anchorage, Alaska, which brought together researchers, agency representatives, and stakeholders to develop strategies for coordinating U.S. observing activities. The workshop was funded primarily by the National Science Foundation's Arctic Sciences Section (previously the Division of Arctic Sciences), with additional support from the North Slope Science Initiative, the Arctic Landscape Conservation Cooperative, the North Pacific Research Board, the Alaska Ocean Observing System, and the Office of Naval Research.
 - ARCUS worked with the workshop Organizing Committee to develop the final workshop report, which includes descriptions of 11 "showcase projects" that would demonstrate effective approaches towards interagency collaboration for the AON. The report also summarizes recommendations on data management, challenges for building a coordinated network, and future directions and opportunities. The report is available at: <http://www.arcus.org/search/aon>.
- **Observing Change Panel (OCP) Facilitation and Support:**
 - Worked with the SSC and OCP Chair Craig Lee to facilitate and track Observing Change Panel discussions.
 - Worked with the OCP to provide input into the SEARCH strategic plan process and draft documents.
 - Scheduled and organized an OCP meeting at AGU in December in San Francisco, CA.

- Worked with OCP co-chair Craig Lee and SSC to provide input on planning for an Arctic Observing Summit.

Science Steering Committee (SSC) Meetings and Support

In addition to the strategic planning activities, ARCUS has managed SEARCH Science Steering Committee (SSC) tasks and planning:

- Organized and developed the agendas for monthly SSC teleconferences, facilitated the monthly calls, distributed call notes and action items.
- Tracked progress and action items for all SSC tasks, provided project management oversight for SSC activities; drafted correspondence and other materials.
- Provided strategic guidance for SSC direction and activities.
- Provided travel support for the SSC chair, H. Eicken:
 - Provided travel support for H. Eicken in April 2012 to travel to the International Polar Year 2012 Conference and Arctic Science Summit Week in Montreal to represent the SEARCH program.
 - Provided travel support for H. Eicken to travel to Washington, D.C. in February 2013 to discuss SEARCH activities with NSF representatives.

SEARCH Website

- Continued content updates and maintenance.
- Transferred all content into a database-backed system.
- Initiated planning for a re-design and structure of the website that is organized around the SEARCH five-year goals.

1.1.b. INTERAGENCY ARCTIC RESEARCH POLICY COMMITTEE (IARPC) ACTIVITIES

- **IARPC Website Development** - ARCUS has worked closely with IARPC staff to determine initial needs and a plan for developing a new website focused on IARPC implementation activities. The website will provide updates on all IARPC activities and will be designed to facilitate conversations across agency and disciplinary boundaries. ARCUS has contracted with a web development firm, Webitects, Inc., who has started work on a user research phase in collaboration with ARCUS.
- **Salary Support for the IARPC Executive Secretary** – ARCUS provided support for the full-time salary and associated costs (e.g., teleconference services, travel) for IARPC

Executive Secretary Sara Bowden through a Professional Services Agreement. The primary responsibility of the Secretary is to provide support to the IARPC Executive Director. The Secretary is responsible for planning, recording, and posting meeting notes for all IARPC principals' and staff group meetings; and will be responsible for providing support in the implementation of the IARPC five-year plan.

- **Additional IARPC Staffing Support** – ARCUS provided 25% salary support for IARPC Secretariat staff Sandy Starkweather through a sub-award. This position ensures that goals of the IARPC research plan are being met and that collaboration with other entities, including state and local government agencies, NGO's, Indigenous groups, and academics is being promoted.

1.2. Arctic Data Coordination

- No activities during the reporting period.

1.3. State of the Arctic Conference

- No activities during the reporting period (task had been completed).

2. NSF ARCTIC SCIENCES SECTION COORDINATION

2.1. ARCSS COORDINATION

- No activities during the reporting period

2.2. BERING SEA RESEARCH COORDINATION

ARCUS provides support to the Bering Sea Project, which is a continuation of the Bering Ecosystem Study (BEST) science planning process.

- ARCUS staff (B. Turner-Bogren) participated in monthly Bering Sea Project teleconferences to remain abreast of program developments.
- ARCUS staff (S. Fox and B. Turner-Bogren) attended Alaska Marine Science Symposium 21-24 January 2013 in Anchorage, Alaska.
- Following a request from Bill Wiseman in March 2012, ARUCS supported one-half the cost of an open-access PDF copy of the first Bering Sea Project (also known as BEST) special journal issue of "Deep-Sea Research Part II." This project was managed by Tom Van Pelt of the North Pacific Research Board (NPRB).
- Provided travel support for Mike Lomas, BEST researcher, to attend Transatlantic Science Meeting 14-15 November in Houston, Texas.

2.3. ARCTIC SOCIAL SCIENCES COORDINATION

The Earth Is Faster Now

The Earth is Faster Now: Indigenous Observations of Arctic Environmental Change (2002), published by ARCUS in cooperation with the Arctic Studies Center, Smithsonian Institution, and compiled and edited by Igor Krupnik and Dyanna Jolly, is a collection of ten papers describing contemporary efforts to document indigenous knowledge of environmental change in the Arctic.

- Continued to distribute book, as requested via orders.

2.4. ARCTIC SECTION SCIENCE MATERIALS

ARCUS, as requested by NSF program staff, will develop information and communication resources such as posters and brochures that reach across geographic, cultural, institutional, and disciplinary barriers to assist planning and integration of diverse research efforts and to improve awareness of NSF-sponsored research in the Arctic.

- No activities were requested by NSF in this period.

2.5. FORUM OF ARCTIC RESEARCH OPERATORS (FARO) DUES

FARO is a forum for information exchange, establishment of cooperation and development of new ideas among the national logistics operators in countries with arctic research activities. NSF provides funds to FARO (through ARCUS) to assist in supporting the activities of the FARO secretariat. The secretariat maintains a website including member contact information and project activity and arranges all relevant meetings in the forum and tracks progress on activities taken on by FARO.

- ARCUS paid for NSF's 2009-2012 FARO dues.

2.6. RESEARCH SUPPORT & LOGISTICS WORKSHOP

The NSF Research Support and Logistics (RSL) program is convening a workshop 7-9 October 2012 in the Washington, D.C. area that gathers representatives of the science community and agencies to discuss changing logistics support needs due to current and emerging scientific developments. The resulting report will provide recommendations on how science support resources should be developed to best advance arctic science. Activities in this reporting period included:

- Developed scope and overall goals of workshop with NSF.
- Held weekly planning calls with RSL staff (starting in January 2013); developed call agendas, reminders, and distributed call notes/action items.
- Developed a workshop planning timeline.
- Developed, with NSF staff, a call for nominations for a workshop organizing committee; posted the announcement to ArcticInfo.

- Tracked and updated a running list of suggestions for workshop participants.
- Provided strategic input on how to utilize existing documents and resources in workshop planning (e.g., previous RSL reports, etc.).
- Drafted a community survey to solicit broad input on RSL issues (will be launched in April 2013).
- Maintained and updated a running task list and action items for all workshop planning topics.

3. ARCTIC SCIENCE EDUCATION

ARCUS has continued to provide an educational leadership role within the arctic community through activities designed to bridge arctic science and education.

3.1. ARCTIC SCIENCE EDUCATION ACTIVITIES

- **Outdoor Days 2012** – Participated in Outdoor Days 2012 (May 2012). Presented a global climate change/arctic related activity and organized the event onsite.
- **IPY Montreal Education and Young Scientists Workshops** – Provided support for some printing and shipping of materials about the Arctic that was disseminated at the 2012 IPY Montreal conference.
- **SACNAS National Conference** – Provided travel for one staff to attend the 2012 SACNAS National Conference on *Science, Technology, and Diversity for a Healthy World*, in Seattle, WA, 11-14 October 2012. ARCUS hosted an exhibit hall booth to share arctic science with nearly 2,000 participants of the meeting and participated in several other arctic education and mentoring activities.
- **AGU Exploration Station** – Provided staff support and minor materials/shipping costs for an arctic and climate change educational booth at the annual AGU Exploration Station, a public outreach activity conducted prior to the AGU Fall Meeting. The event was free and open to members of the San Francisco public.
- **Arctic Ocean Ecosystem Workshop** – ARCUS partnered with the Centers for Ocean Sciences Education Excellence, the Alaska Ocean Observing System, and the North Pacific Research Board to hold an Arctic Ocean Ecosystem Workshop in Barrow, Alaska in 2012. This workshop brought together teachers, scientists, and local residents and resulted in an online collection of educational resources (lesson plans, videos, etc.) focused on marine and climate change science for the Arctic Ocean. Products developed through the workshop included a collection of resources (lesson, multi-media, presentations) stored on the PolarTREC Learning Resources Database and shared through COSEE and NOAA.
- **Extreme Cold Weather (ECW) Gear Kit** – Continued mailing ECW kits to teachers and the public as requested.

- **Webinars** – Facilitated webinars with APECS for early career scientists and educators.
- **Polar Education Mailing List** – Maintained the ARCUS Polar Education List, which provides a venue for educators, researchers, and learners to exchange information about opportunities, challenges, methods, resources, important events, and other useful topics.

3.2. Arctic Visiting Speakers' Series

ARCUS initiated the Arctic Visiting Speakers' (AVS) Series in 2000 to increase communication and collaboration among the dispersed arctic research community and to nurture better understanding and communication between arctic researchers and arctic community residents.

- Supported Karsten Heuer to travel to New Hampshire and Vermont on a multi-stop tour, including presentations on "*Canoe Exploration of the Canadian North*" and related northern topics. Total audience was 330 of students, faculty, and general public.
- Supported Dr. Kathleen Osgood to travel to Yakutsk, Russia to work with students and faculty at North-Eastern Federal University, Mirny Polytechnical Institute, Nerungry Technical University, and Republican College. She delivered a series of lectures and activities that focused on oral traditions. Total audience: over 100 students and faculty.
- Supported Leonard Kamerling to travel to Western Oregon University in Monmouth, Oregon, and other venues. The feature event of this tour was a screening of Kamerling's documentary film "Drums of Winter" followed by a question-and-answer session. Total audience: 180 students, faculty and general public.
- Supported Dr. Jennifer Burns to travel to Memphis, Tennessee to participate in a week's worth of education and public outreach activities. Dr. Burns visited a museum and many local schools for presentations on "Passport to Antarctica – Where Adventure Meets Seal Science" and related topics. Total audience: 586 elementary students, teachers, and general public, plus news interviews.
- Supported Dr. George Archibald, co-founder of the International Crane Foundation, to travel to Fairbanks, Alaska to speak and participate at the 2012 Tanana Valley Sandhill Crane Festival. There he spoke about "Cranes in the Arctic" and gave other presentations at the festival. Total audience: 275 general public and UAF students.
- Supported Dr. Rolf Gradinger to travel to Sitka, Alaska for educational and outreach activities as part of the Sitka WhaleFest, with talks on "Trials, Tribulations, & Triumphs of Arctic Research" and related topics. Total audience: 650 general public, students, and teachers.
- Supported Dr. Anne Jensen to travel to Valdez, Alaska to talk about arctic archaeology to

audiences of all ages at schools, a college, and museum. Total audience: 415 students, teachers, and public, plus listeners of public radio.

- Supported Dr. David Klein to travel to Florida State University for a talk and webinar on wildlife in Alaska and the Arctic. Total audience: 85 students, secondary teachers, and faculty.
- Supported Henry Huntington to travel to Nerungry, Russia to work with several audiences. Henry spoke on topics including the changing roles of humans and the arctic environment, differences and similarities between arctic peoples, and traditional ecological knowledge in the Arctic. Total audience: 250 students and faculty.
- Supported Dr. Kirk Dombrowski to travel to Providence, Rhode Island and lecture at Brown University and a museum on the topic of arctic governance. Total audience: 50 students, faculty, and general public.
- Continual updates to the AVS website and development of outreach materials and activities, including development of an AVS logo; outreach via information mailings, poster/flyers, and several announcements; and development of an AVS Facebook page.

Detailed information on tours can be found at: <http://www.arcus.org/arctic-visiting-speakers/all/tours>.

4. INFORMATION AND OUTREACH

ARCUS serves as a communication channel providing information about current research activities and arctic issues to the scientific community, agencies, and the public.

4.1. *Witness the Arctic* Newsletter

- **Completed Spring 2012 Issue** – Finalized and released spring 2012 issue on 20 June (Volume 16, Number 2): <http://www.arcus.org/witness-the-arctic/2012/2>.
- **Completed Fall 2012 Issue** – Finalized and released fall 2012 issue on 14 November (Volume 16, Number 3) <http://www.arcus.org/witness-the-arctic/2012/3>.
- **Completed Winter 2013 Issue** – Finalized winter 2013 issue for release on 5 March (Volume 17, Number 1): <http://www.arcus.org/witness-the-arctic/2013/1>.

4.2. Website and Internet Resources

The ARCUS website provides essential information and resources for the diverse and geographically distributed arctic research community and serves several thousand pages and files. The website is the focal point for educational programs, various community science planning efforts, and provides important information and resources to the research community about research programs, meetings, community activities, and publications. The website provides

program information; electronic copies of publications; agendas, abstracts, and participant lists from meetings, the online calendar, and other resources.

- Continued to update website, develop new content, and improve functionality. Increasingly used website-tracking software to analyze website use patterns, using Google analytics, and increased use of dynamic content.
- Finished moving "static content" into a system that allows for more dynamic functionality (Drupal content management framework).
- Maintained and Improved the Online Arctic Calendar –
The online calendar provides an up-to-date and comprehensive calendar of arctic meetings and conferences: <http://calendar.arcus.org/>. Calendar events were added as they became available through ArcticInfo, the International Arctic Science Committee (IASC), the Arctic Ocean Sciences Board (AOSB), as well as any submissions by individuals. Updated the event submission form and process, and began improvements to the search and filter functions (to be released May 2013).

4.3. ArcticInfo Mailing List

ARCUS continues to develop and maintain ArcticInfo, the primary electronic mailing list for the arctic research community. ArcticInfo provides timely information about funding opportunities, important events, publications, position announcements, and other news. All postings are archived in a searchable directory on the ARCUS website.

- Continued to develop and maintain the mailing list, including receiving, editing, and posting 508 announcements to the list between 1 March 2013 and 28 February 2013.
- Increased email subscribers by a net total of 178 people. There are currently just over 7,000 subscribers.
- Began planning for streamlining the announcement submission and distribution processes, including an online submittal form and additional staff trained to write and post ArcticInfo announcements.

4.4. Directory of Arctic Researchers

The Directory of Arctic Researchers facilitates networking and collaboration in arctic research and education efforts between individual investigators, institutions, funding agencies, and arctic stakeholders. The contents of the Directory, which includes information on over 4,000 U.S. and international arctic researchers, are developed through surveys of individual arctic researchers and institutions (see website at: <http://www.arcus.org/researcher/index.html>).

- Continued to develop and maintain the Directory of Arctic Researchers. Distributed PDFs to community members upon request, and frequently directed people to the Directory search site to find contacts in specific research fields, geographic locations, etc.

4.5. Internet Media Archive

The ARCUS Internet Media Archive (IMA) is a collection of polar-relevant photos, graphics, videos, and presentations that have been compiled for various purposes and are shared through the ARCUS website at: <http://media.arcus.org>.

- Continued to add photos, videos, and other media files.
- Planned the transition of the Internet Media Archive from a stand-alone entity/project to one integrated with the full ARCUS website.

4.6. Arctic Community Outreach

ARCUS continues to conduct a number of outreach activities that disseminate timely information about arctic research to scientists, policy and decision-makers, educators and the public, and that build supportive networks among those groups to advance international arctic research efforts and our understanding of the Arctic.

- **Arctic Community Meeting Room at AGU** - Organized the Arctic Community Meeting Room at the 2012 Fall Meeting of the American Geophysical Union. The room encourages scientific collaboration and makes face-to-face meetings of opportunity possible for the arctic research community. In 2012, the room hosted 28 meetings with at least 325 participants.

5. CORE SUPPORT

Core Support includes program activities that simultaneously support multiple cooperative agreement projects and cannot be attributed to a specific project.

- Continued support of direct activities that address multiple tasks and programs, including portions of the Executive Director, Director of Programs, and System Administrator salaries.
- Provided partial speaker support for 2012 Arctic Forum panelists. The Arctic Forum was held in conjunction with AGU's Science Policy Conference, May 2012 in Washington, D.C.: <http://spc.agu.org/2012/agenda/>.

Arctic Research Consortium of the United States, Inc.
 ARC-0618885
 Task: NSF Form 1030 Summary

4/9/13 13:42		APRIL - Dec	2009	2010	2011	2012	
From:			Jan - Dec				
To:		YEAR 1	YEAR 2	YEAR 3	YEAR 4	YEAR 5	Total Project
Form 1030 Category		YTD Actuals					
Salaries							
President	A1	-	-	-	-	-	-
Executive director	A2	45,875	69,682	85,772	93,272	87,282	381,883
Other professionals	B2	234,751	356,293	354,514	370,917	349,146	1,665,621
Student	B3	30,926	2,623	-	-	-	33,549
Clerical	B5	14,084	54,255	46,375	20,531	22,149	157,394
Total salaries		325,636	482,852	486,661	484,720	458,577	2,238,447
Fringe Benefits							
Total salaries and fringe benefits	C	130,017	212,927	210,894	227,763	212,511	994,112
		455,654	695,779	697,556	712,483	671,088	3,232,559
Permanent Equipment							
	D	20,800	-	-	4,910	-	25,710
Travel (domestic)							
	E1	70,614	53,823	78,595	41,193	55,999	300,224
Travel (foreign)							
	E2	-	-	6,951	2,939	-	9,889
Participant Support Costs							
Stipends	F1	400	400	1,000	2,700	10,350	14,850
Travel	F2	61,607	33,752	99,480	24,769	56,444	276,051
Subsistence	F3	60,483	21,318	73,415	18,201	34,363	207,779
Total participant costs		122,490	55,470	173,894	45,670	101,157	498,681
Other Direct Costs							
Materials and supplies	G1	36,911	12,277	19,786	6,802	4,880	80,656
Publication cost/ docum/dissemin	G2	18,968	45,007	8,653	2,449	9,607	84,683
Consultant services	G3	40,575	63,027	21,348	4,425	55,106	184,480
Computer services	G4	35,469	43,606	35,949	41,263	32,486	188,773
Subcontracts	G5	101,148	13,598	-	5,933	4,310	124,989
Other	G6	136,850	94,490	182,907	18,167	240,702	673,116
Total other direct costs		369,921	272,005	268,642	79,038	347,091	1,336,696
Total direct costs	H	1,039,478	1,077,076	1,225,638	886,235	1,175,336	5,403,762
Indirect Costs							
	I	348,115	366,121	473,122	357,235	458,868	2,003,462
Total direct and indirect costs	J	1,387,594	1,443,197	1,698,761	1,243,467	1,634,204	7,407,223
NSF FUNDED BUDGET							9,312,684
BALANCE OF BUDGET =							1,905,461
Ties to FFR Dec							
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Arctic Research Consortium of the United States, Inc.
 ARC-0618885
 Task: NSF Task Summary

		4/9/13 13:42						
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		YEAR 1	YEAR 2	YEAR 3	YEAR 4	YEAR 5	TOTAL	
		YTD Actuals	YTD Actuals	YTD Actuals	YTD Actuals	YTD Actuals	PROJECT	
1 Arctic Community Science Planning								
1.1	SEARCH Coordination						F64 F65 F70	
	Salaries and Fringe Benefits	79,639	177,144	182,422	272,361	257,359	968,924	
	Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-	-	
	Travel (domestic)	22,219	22,429	17,064	16,923	23,751	102,386	
	Travel (foreign)	-	-	2,499	1,469	-	3,968	
	Participant Support Costs	54,964	45,903	72,140	24,520	35,034	232,561	
	Other Direct Costs	49,820	24,834	41,435	32,099	131,975	280,162	
	Total direct costs	206,642	270,309	315,561	347,371	448,119	1,588,002	
	Indirect Costs	78,524	95,117	123,071	141,707	175,374	613,792	
	Total direct and indirect costs	285,165	365,426	438,631	489,078	623,493	2,201,793	
							-	
							-	
1.2	Arctic Data Coordination						F68	
	Salaries and Fringe Benefits	5,189	1,084	-	-	-	6,273	
	Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-	-	
	Travel (domestic)	3,007	(383)	-	-	-	2,625	
	Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-	-	-	
	Participant Support Costs	-	-	-	-	-	-	
	Other Direct Costs	2,000	12,078	-	-	-	14,078	
	Total direct costs	10,196	12,778	-	-	-	22,974	
	Indirect Costs	3,874	296	(1)	-	-	4,168	
	Total direct and indirect costs	14,070	13,074	(1)	-	-	27,143	
							-	
							-	
1.3	State of the ARCTIC						F63	
	Salaries and Fringe Benefits		139,865	215,278	44,036	-	399,179	
	Permanent Equipment		-	-	-	-	-	
	Travel (domestic)		3,615	37,503	-	-	41,117	
	Travel (foreign)		-	-	-	-	-	
	Participant Support Costs		-	65,286	-	-	65,286	
	Other Direct Costs		59,957	151,352	(20,677)	4,406	195,038	
	Total direct costs		203,436	469,419	23,359	4,406	700,620	
	Indirect Costs		73,506	177,945	9,533	1,727	262,711	
	Total direct and indirect costs		276,942	647,364	32,892	6,133	963,331	
							-	
							-	
2 NSF Arctic Sciences Section Coordination								
2.1	ARCSS Program Coordination						F73	
2.1.1	ARCSS Coordination							
	Salaries and Fringe Benefits	13,245	51,542	9,043	19,916	141	93,886	
	Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-	-	
	Travel (domestic)	3,851	2,584	197	-	-	6,632	
	Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-	-	-	
	Participant Support Costs	6,734	2,279	21,709	-	-	30,722	
	Other Direct Costs	120,092	16,440	4,127	6,758	825	148,241	
	Total direct costs	143,922	72,845	35,076	26,674	966	279,482	
	Indirect Costs	16,254	13,394	14,144	8,381	328	52,500	
	Total direct and indirect costs	160,176	86,238	49,219	35,055	1,293	331,982	
							-	
							-	
2.2	Arctic Natural Sciences Program Coordination						F66	
2.2.1	Bering Sea Research Coordination							
	Salaries and Fringe Benefits	2,632	17,987	9,482	3,667	1,890	35,657	
	Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-	-	
	Travel (domestic)	989	1,109	4,092	698	819	7,708	
	Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-	-	-	
	Participant Support Costs	8,429	5,012	6,997	3,488	3,592	27,518	
	Other Direct Costs	751	887	1,246	2,443	4,525	9,853	
	Total direct costs	12,801	24,995	21,816	10,296	10,826	80,735	
	Indirect Costs	4,864	3,798	8,566	4,172	4,256	25,656	
	Total direct and indirect costs	17,665	28,794	30,382	14,468	15,082	106,392	

Arctic Research Consortium of the United States, Inc.
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Task: NSF Task Summary

		YEAR 1	YEAR 2	YEAR 3	YEAR 4	YEAR 5	TOTAL	
		YTD Actuals	PROJECT					
2.3	Arctic Social Sciences Program Coordination							
2.3.1	Arctic Social Sciences Coordination							F79
	Salaries and Fringe Benefits	-	-	148	-	-	148	
	Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-	-	
	Travel (domestic)	-	-	-	-	-	-	
	Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-	-	-	
	Participant Support Costs	-	-	-	-	-	-	
	Other Direct Costs	-	-	5,444	-	-	5,444	
	Total direct costs	-	-	5,593	-	-	5,593	
	Indirect Costs	-	-	2,168	(5)	-	2,163	
	Total direct and indirect costs	-	-	7,761	(5)	-	7,755	
2.4	Arctic Section Science Materials							
2.4.1	Arctic Section Science Materials							F71
	Salaries and Fringe Benefits	-	-	50	285	37	372	
	Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-	-	
	Travel (domestic)	-	-	-	-	-	-	
	Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-	-	-	
	Participant Support Costs	-	-	-	-	-	-	
	Other Direct Costs	-	1,000	-	-	-	1,000	
	Total direct costs	-	1,000	50	285	37	1,372	
	Indirect Costs	-	-	19	117	14	149	
	Total direct and indirect costs	-	1,000	69	402	51	1,522	
2.5	Forum for Arctic Research Operators							
2.5.1	FARO							F72
	Other Direct Costs					116,353	116,353	
	Total direct costs					116,353	116,353	
	Indirect Costs					45,684	45,684	
	Total direct and indirect costs					162,037	162,037	
2.6	RSL Workshop Washington DC Spring of 2013							F74
	Salaries and Fringe Benefits					499	499	
	Permanent Equipment					-	-	
	Travel (domestic)					-	-	
	Travel (foreign)					-	-	
	Participant Support Costs					-	-	
	Other Direct Costs					-	-	
	Total direct costs					499	499	
	Indirect Costs					200	200	
	Total direct and indirect costs					699	699	
3 Arctic Science Education								
3.1	Arctic Science Education Activities							F85
	Salaries and Fringe Benefits	8,790	8,692	9,991	6,901	13,144	47,519	
	Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-	-	
	Travel (domestic)	6,763	6,410	1,363	1,270	-	15,806	
	Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-	-	-	
	Participant Support Costs	5,556	(168)	-	-	13,149	18,537	
	Other Direct Costs	3,655	2,343	1,227	1,711	2,386	11,322	
	Total direct costs	24,763	17,277	12,581	9,882	28,679	93,182	
	Indirect Costs	9,410	6,565	4,878	4,034	11,212	36,100	
	Total direct and indirect costs	34,173	23,846	17,460	13,917	39,891	129,287	
3.2	Arctic Visiting Speakers							F86
	Salaries and Fringe Benefits	2,033	13,973	11,868	23,211	26,655	77,739	
	Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-	-	
	Travel (domestic)	-	-	-	-	-	-	
	Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-	-	-	
	Participant Support Costs	2,502	1,886	7,763	17,662	13,363	43,176	
	Other Direct Costs	919	2,150	49	500	234	3,852	
	Total direct costs	5,454	18,009	19,679	41,373	40,251	124,767	
	Indirect Costs	2,073	6,084	7,708	16,907	15,644	48,416	
	Total direct and indirect costs	7,527	24,093	27,387	58,280	55,896	173,182	
4 Information and Outreach								
4.1	Witness the Arctic Newsletters							F90
	Salaries and Fringe Benefits	21,506	22,509	56,411	81,354	98,371	280,151	
	Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-	-	
	Travel (domestic)	-	-	706	-	-	706	
	Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-	-	-	
	Participant Support Costs	-	-	-	-	-	-	
	Other Direct Costs	15,355	55,796	2,598	-	500	74,249	
	Total direct costs	36,861	78,305	59,715	81,354	98,871	355,105	
	Indirect Costs	14,007	29,756	23,255	33,213	38,592	138,823	
	Total direct and indirect costs	50,868	108,061	82,970	114,567	137,462	493,928	

Arctic Research Consortium of the United States, Inc.
ARC-0618885
Task: NSF Task Summary

HW:\Users\arcus\Desktop\CA_Report_2012-2013\NSF_Annual_Report_FYE_2012.xlsx\NSF Form 1030 Summary							
	YEAR 1	YEAR 2	YEAR 3	YEAR 4	YEAR 5	TOTAL	
	YTD Actuals	PROJECT					

Arctic Research Consortium of the United States, Inc.
ARC-0618885
Task: NSF Task Summary

HW:\Users\arcus\Desktop\CA_Report_2012-2013\NSF_Annual_Report_FYE_2012.xlsx\NSF Form 1030 Summary		YEAR 1	YEAR 2	YEAR 3	YEAR 4	YEAR 5	TOTAL	
		YTD Actuals	PROJECT					
4.2	Website/Internet Resources							F91
	Salaries and Fringe Benefits	108,889	55,502	36,694	31,445	36,154	268,684	
	Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-	-	
	Travel (domestic)	85	4,262	1,851	-	2,261	8,458	
	Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-	-	-	
	Participant Support Costs	-	-	-	-	-	-	
	Other Direct Costs	-	5,772	27,209	27,727	24,562	85,269	
	Total direct costs	108,974	65,535	65,754	59,172	62,976	362,411	
	Indirect Costs	41,410	23,003	25,467	24,152	24,512	138,545	
	Total direct and indirect costs	150,384	88,539	91,221	83,324	87,488	500,956	
4.3	Arctic Info Listserver							F92
	Salaries and Fringe Benefits	14,334	30,906	25,987	34,954	27,759	133,940	
	Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-	-	
	Travel (domestic)	-	-	430	-	-	430	
	Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-	-	-	
	Participant Support Costs	-	-	-	-	-	-	
	Other Direct Costs	-	-	157	-	-	157	
	Total direct costs	14,334	30,906	26,575	34,954	27,759	134,528	
	Indirect Costs	5,447	11,744	10,323	14,258	10,864	52,637	
	Total direct and indirect costs	19,781	42,650	36,897	49,212	38,623	187,164	
4.4	Directory of Arctic Researchers							F93
	Salaries and Fringe Benefits	1,002	6,780	3,227	1,647	5,862	18,518	
	Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-	-	
	Travel (domestic)	-	-	-	-	-	-	
	Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-	-	-	
	Participant Support Costs	-	-	-	-	-	-	
	Other Direct Costs	-	-	-	-	-	-	
	Total direct costs	1,002	6,780	3,227	1,647	5,862	18,518	
	Indirect Costs	381	2,576	1,235	674	2,294	7,160	
	Total direct and indirect costs	1,383	9,356	4,462	2,321	8,157	25,679	
4.5	Internet Media Archive							F95
	Salaries and Fringe Benefits	7,037	29,196	29,731	38,790	53,342	158,097	
	Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-	-	
	Travel (domestic)	-	-	-	-	-	-	
	Travel (foreign)	-	-	-	-	-	-	
	Participant Support Costs	-	-	-	-	-	-	
	Other Direct Costs	50	-	-	-	-	50	
	Total direct costs	7,087	29,196	29,731	38,790	53,342	158,147	
	Indirect Costs	2,693	11,095	11,556	15,841	20,823	62,007	
	Total direct and indirect costs	9,780	40,291	41,287	54,631	74,166	220,154	
4.6	Community Outreach							F94 F88
	Salaries and Fringe Benefits	83,312	18,082	14,401	20,891	14,695	151,381	
	Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-	-	
	Travel (domestic)	33,341	8,073	9,417	9,543	4,130	64,504	
	Travel (foreign)	-	-	1,953	-	-	1,953	
	Participant Support Costs	44,304	-	-	-	23,866	68,170	
	Other Direct Costs	74,818	35,483	14,717	12,416	12,103	149,537	
	Total direct costs	235,776	61,637	40,487	42,850	54,794	435,544	
	Indirect Costs	89,595	19,242	16,430	17,498	21,026	163,791	
	Total direct and indirect costs	325,371	80,879	56,917	60,348	75,820	599,336	
5 Core Support								F60
5.1	Core Support							
	Salaries and Fringe Benefits	108,045	122,518	92,823	133,025	135,182	591,591	
	Permanent Equipment	20,800	-	-	4,910	-	25,710	
	Travel (domestic)	359	5,725	5,971	12,759	25,038	49,852	
	Travel (foreign)	-	-	2,499	1,469	-	3,968	
	Participant Support Costs	-	558	-	-	12,154	12,711	
	Other Direct Costs	102,349	55,266	19,082	16,061	49,223	241,982	
	Total direct costs	231,553	184,066	120,376	168,224	221,596	925,815	
	Indirect Costs	87,990	69,945	46,361	66,752	86,318	357,366	
	Total direct and indirect costs	319,543	254,011	166,736	234,976	307,914	1,283,181	
TOTAL PROGRAMS								
	Salaries and Fringe Benefits	455,654	695,779	697,556	712,483	671,088	3,232,559	
	Permanent Equipment	20,800	-	-	4,910	-	25,710	
	Travel (domestic)	70,614	53,823	78,595	41,193	55,999	300,224	
	Travel (foreign)	-	-	6,951	2,939	-	9,889	
	Participant Support Costs	122,490	55,470	173,894	45,670	101,157	498,681	
	Other Direct Costs	369,921	272,005	268,642	79,038	347,091	1,336,696	
	Total direct costs	1,039,478	1,077,076	1,225,638	886,232	1,175,336	5,403,762	
	Indirect Costs	348,115	366,121	473,122	357,235	458,868	2,003,462	
	Total direct and indirect costs	1,387,594	1,443,197	1,698,761	1,243,467	1,634,204	7,407,223	

Arctic Research Consortium of the United States, Inc.
ARC-0618885
Task: NSF Costs by Category

	A	B	C	K	Q	W	AC	AI	AJ
1									
2									
3				YEAR 1	YEAR 2	Year 3	YEAR 4	YEAR 5	Total
4				YTD Actuals	YTD Actuals	Actuals	YTD Actuals	YTD Actuals	Project
5									
6									
7	1 Arctic Community Science Planning								
8	1.1	SEARCH Coordination		206,642	270,309	315,561	347,371	448,119	1,588,002
9	1.2	Arctic Data Coordination		10,196	12,778	-	141,707	-	164,682
10	1.3	State of the Arctic			203,436	469,419	489,078	4,406	1,166,339
11		SubTotal Direct Costs		216,838	486,524	784,979	978,156	452,525	2,919,023
12		Indirect Costs		82,398	168,918	301,014	151,240	177,101	880,671
13		TOTAL		299,236	655,442	1,085,994	521,970	629,626	3,192,268
14									
15	2 NSF Arctic Sciences Section Coordination								
16	2.1.1	ARCSS Program Coordination		143,922	72,845	35,076	26,674	966	279,482
17	2.2.1	Arctic Natural Sciences Program Coordination		12,801	24,995	21,816	10,296	10,826	80,735
18	2.3.1	Arctic Social Sciences Coordination		-	-	5,593	-	-	5,593
19	2.4.1	Arctic Section Science Materials		-	1,000	50	285	37	1,372
20	2.5.1	FARO funding		-	-	-	-	116,353	116,353
21	2.6.1	RSL Workshop Washington DC.		-	-	-	-	499	499
22		SubTotal Direct Costs		156,723	98,840	62,534	37,256	128,681	484,034
23		Indirect Costs		21,117	17,192	24,896	12,665	50,481	126,352
24		TOTAL		177,840	116,032	87,430	49,920	179,162	610,385
25									
26	3 Arctic Science Education								
27	3.1	Arctic Science Education Activities		24,763	17,277	12,581	9,882	28,679	93,182
28	3.2	Arctic Visiting Speakers		5,454	18,009	19,679	41,373	40,251	124,767
29		SubTotal Direct Costs		30,218	35,286	32,260	51,255	68,930	217,949
30		Indirect Costs		11,483	12,649	12,586	20,941	26,857	84,515
31		TOTAL		41,701	47,935	44,846	72,196	95,787	302,464
32									
33	4 Information and Outreach								
34	4.1	Witness the Arctic Newsletters		36,861	78,305	59,715	81,354	98,871	355,105
35	4.2	Website/Internet Resources		108,974	65,535	65,754	59,172	62,976	362,411
36	4.3	Arctic Info Listserver		14,334	30,906	26,575	34,954	27,759	134,528
37	4.4	Directory of Arctic Researchers		1,002	6,780	3,227	1,647	5,862	18,518
38	4.5	Internet Media Archive		7,087	29,196	29,731	38,790	53,342	158,147
39	4.6	Community Outreach		235,776	61,637	40,487	42,850	54,794	435,544
40		SubTotal Direct Costs		404,034	272,360	225,489	258,767	303,604	1,464,253
41		Indirect Costs		153,533	97,417	88,265	105,637	118,111	562,963
42		TOTAL		557,567	369,776	313,754	364,404	421,715	2,027,216
43									
44	5 Core Support								
45	5.1	Core Support		231,553	184,066	120,376	168,224	221,596	925,815
46		SubTotal Direct Costs		231,553	184,066	120,376	168,224	221,596	925,815
47		Indirect Costs		87,990	69,945	46,361	66,752	86,318	357,366
48		TOTAL		319,543	254,011	166,736	234,976	307,914	1,283,181
49									
50		TOTAL COSTS		1,387,594	1,443,197	1,698,761	1,243,467	1,634,204	7,407,223
51									
52									
53								NSF FUNDED BUDGET	9,312,684
54									
55								BALANCE OF BUDGET =	1,905,461